

KIMYO FANINI O'QITISHDA REPRODUKTIV USUL

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2 son kasb hunar maktabi kimyo fani o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Maqolada kimyo fanini o'qitishda yangi pedagogik metodlardan foydalanish, reproduktiv usullarni ishlatish mug'imligi va laboratoriya mashg'ulotlari fanni chuqur o'rganishga yordam berishi masalalariga to'xtab o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kimyo, fan, muammo, baholash, reproduktiv

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается использование новых педагогических методов в преподавании химии, возможность использования репродуктивных методов, а также вопросы о том, как лабораторные занятия могут помочь углубленному изучению науки.

Ключевые слова: Химия, наука, проблема, оценка, репродуктивная.

Abstract: The article discusses the use of new pedagogical methods in teaching chemistry, the importance of using reproductive methods, and the role of laboratory exercises in the in-depth study of science.

Keywords: Chemistry, science, problem, assessment, reproductive

O'qitishning reproduktiv va muammoli-izlanish usullari eng avvalo, o'quvchilarning yangi tushuncha, hodisa va qonunlarni bilishdagi ijodiy faolliklari darajasini baholash asosida qismlarga ajratiladi. Reproductive usullar birinchi navbatda, o'quvchilarning o'quv materialini mustahkamroq eslab qolishlarini ta'minlash, bilishga doir faoliyatni bevosita boshqarish, kamchiliklarni tez aniqlash uchun amaliy ko'nikma va malakalarni tarkib toptirish maqsadida qo'llaniladi. Reproductive usullar ayniqsa, o'quv materialining mazmuni asosan axborot xarakterida bo'lsa, amaliy harakatlarning usullarini ta'riflash, o'quvchilarning

bilimlarini mustaqil qidirib olib bilishlari uchun juda yangi hisoblansa, vaziyatlarni hal qilish uchun tayyâr bilimlar yo'q bo'lsa samarali qo'llanadi.

Xlorli oksiyoki alkosiguruh almashtirish masalasini ko'rib chiqsak: Bu reaksiya fenol, dinitrofenol, 2-amino-4-nitrofenol va boshqalar sintezida ishlatiladi. 70% fenol xlorbenzolni kumol usuli bilan gidrolizlab olinadi. Xlorli hosilaning tabiatiga qarab atmosfera bosimida èki avtoklavda bosim ostida aromatik xlorli birikmani 10%li suvli ishqor èki soda eritmasida qizdirish yo'li bilan olinadi. hosil bo'lgan mahsulot vodorod xlorid yoki sulfat kislota qo'shib, so'ng filtrlab ajratib olinadi. Alkillash va arillash reaksiyasi Amin-, oksi yoki sulfogidril tarkibidagi vodorod o'rniga alkil èki aril qoldig'ini kelishi bilan boradigan reaksiyalarga alkillash èki arillash deb ataladi. Funktsional guruhning turiga qarab N -, O-, va S- alkillash reaksiyasi deb ataladi.

Alkillash reaksiyasi elektrofil o'rin olish mexanizmi bo'yicha boradi:

Arillash reaksiyasi umumiy ko'rinishda quyidagi tenglama bilan ifodalanadi:

Aromatik aminlar hosilalari ichida mono- va dimetil, mono- va dietil, oksietillarning ahamiyati kattadir. Aminoguruhni alkillaganda uning aromatik yadroga ta'siri kuchayadi. Aromatik aminlarni metillash va etillash spirtlar ta'sirida 2000S 30 atm. bosim ostida 5-10 soat ichida biroz vodorod xlorid èki sulfat kislota qo'shgan xolda qizitish yo'li bilan olib boriladi. Alkillovchi omil sifatida galoidalkillar ishlatilsa, jarayon kislota ajralishi bilan boradi.

Tafakkurning reproduktivlik xarakteri o'qituvchi yoki boshqa manba orqali xabar kilinadigan o'quv axborotlarini faol idrok qilinishi va eslab qolinishini nazarda tutadi. Bu usullarni o'ziga xos moddiy asosi bo'lib hisoblanadigan o'qitishning og'zaki, ko'rgazmali va amaliy usullaridan foydalanmay qo'llash mumkin emas.

Hikoya usuli reproduktiv tuzilganda o'qituvchi omillarni, dalillarni, tushunchalarning ta'rifini tayèr holda beradi, e'tiborni ayniqsa mustahkam o'zlashtirib olinishi zarur bo'lgan asosiy tomonlarga qaratadi. Ma'ruza ham xuddi shunday tarzda tuziladi: o'qituvchi muayyan ilmiy ma'lumotlarni baèn qiladi, doskaga tegishli èzuvlarni bitadi, o'quvchilar esa ularni qisqacha yozib oladilar.

Reproduktiv xarakterdagi amaliy ishlar shunisi bilan farq qiladiki, bu ishlarning davomida o'quvchilar namunaga ko'ra ilgari èki yaqindagina o'zlashtirilgan bilimlarni qo'llaydilar. Reprodukativ mashqlar amaliy ko'nikma va malakalarni namuna bo'yicha bir necha bor takrorlash orqali mustahkamlashga ayniqsa samarali ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Laboratoriya mashq ishlari. Laboratoriya mashqlari har tomonlama tajribalar, laboratoriya ishlari, amaliètlar, o'qitishning texnik vositalari va o'quv qurollar turidagi boshqa asbob-uskunalar bilan mashg'ulotlar tarzida o'tkaziladi.

Laboratoriya usuli o'qitish jaraènida o'quvchilarga atrofni o'rab olgan obyektiv borliqdagi narsa va hodisalar, ularning shakli, hajmi, tarkibi, tuzilishi, o'zgarish va rivojlanish qonuniyatlari haqida yangi-yangi bilimlar berish, o'zlashtirilaètgan ilmiy bilimlarni mustahkamlash hamda tegishli ko'nikma va malakalar bilan qurollantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Laboratoriya mashg'uloti odatda maxsus jihozlangan xonada hamda tegishli apparat, asbob-uskunalar; kolba, o'lchov asboblari va boshqa qurollar bilan ta'minlangan o'quv xonalarida olib boriladi.

Laboratoriya mashg'ulotlarini to'g'ri tashkil qilish natijasida o'quvchilarning tevarak-atrofdagi narsa va hodisalarni mustaqil kuzatishga bo'lgan qiziqishlari kuchayadi, mustaqillik, faollik va tashabbuskorliklari ortadi. Amaliy ish tajribalari - ko'nikma, malakalari hosil qilinadi. Mehnat madaniyati rivojlanadi. Laboratoriya usulining boshqa o'qitish usullaridan farqi shundaki, bu usul bilan ish ko'rilganda har qaysi o'quvchi (yakka holda èki o'quvchidar guruhi) nimanidir mustaqil,

shaxsan tajriba qilib ko'radi. Dars boshdan-o'ëq o'qituvchi rahbarligi ostida o'quvchilarning mustaqil tajriba o'tkazishlariga qaratilgan bo'ladi.

Muammoli vaziyat yaratish usullari. Muammoli ta'lim deyilganda o'quv materialini o'quvchilar ongida ilmiy izlanishga o'xshash bilish vazifalari va muammolari paydo bo'ladigan qilib o'rganish tushuniladi. O'quvchining fikrlash faoliyatida mantiqiy to'g'ri, ilmiy xulosalarni izlash va o'zlashtirishga rag'batlantiradigan muammoli vaziyatlar vujudga keladi. Paydo bo'laëtgan muammoni hal qilish uchun, u o'rganiladigan qoidalarni to'g'ri tushunib olishga intiladi.

Har qanday ta'lim o'quvchi uchun muammolidir, chunki ta'lim o'quvchini unga hozirgacha noma'lum bo'lgan narsa bilan tanishtiradi: o'quvchi yangi materialni o'zlashtirishi, o'qituvchi va unga qo'yilgan talablarini bajarishi kerak, albatta.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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